

ART STUDIES

POINT OF VIEW, PLOT, AND STRUCTURE: REGIONAL CULTURAL EXPRESSION STRATEGIES IN INNER MONGOLIAN NATIONAL FILMS OF THE 21ST CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

Since the beginning of the 21st century, inner Mongolian films have decisively explored and portrayed the vibrant cultural life of ethnic regions. These films leverage distinct perspectives, compelling plots, and well-structured narratives to powerfully convey their histories. This article reveals that viewpoints can be explored for purposes beyond merely reflecting a region's culture, inviting us to expand our understanding and appreciation of diverse experiences. An appropriate and dramatic plot will evoke national and regional culture into the audience's mind with the plot, giving a lasting impact. The linear causality structure allows for establishing and expanding regional culture alongside its framework, which becomes an organic component of the structure and an object for latent expression. The plot structure emphasizes regional culture as a central theme in the film, contributing to a "documentary" style. The best structure for showcasing a region's culture depends on the filmmaker's creative intent, communicative goals, and other relevant factors.

Keywords: inner Mongolian national film, national culture, actions, viewpoint, structure.

In general, "minority regional culture" refers to a particular cultural heritage with a lengthy history, distinct personality, and lasting influence in a minority territory. This includes local ecology, folklore, traditions, practices, and other material and natural culture types. Ideas like "inner inner Mongolian national cinema" have been continuously discussed in scholarly forums. Wang Zhimin proposed three principles, namely "one fundamental principle" (culture principle) and "two guarantee principles" (author principle, subject matter principle), to judge whether a film can be classified as a "minority film." [1] The inner Mongolian films discussed in this article were written, directed, and acted by inner Mongolians, and they reflect their culture in terms of culture and content.

Since the new century, as globalization and modernity have permeated present life conditions, the inner Mongolian people's lifestyle, cultural appearance, folk practices, and other regional cultures have faced significant challenges. Since the turn of the century, inner Mongolian national cinema has focused greatly on expressing divisions between cultures and has done an excellent job of reminding the general public to be mindful of the preservation and transmission of the country's culture. Inner Mongolian films should depict the local culture when conveying cultural problems in the twenty-first century. This article examines each region's performance and role in inner Mongolian cinema from various angles, plots, and structures to obtain a more comprehensive and in-depth understanding of regional cultural expression tactics in inner Mongolian cinema.

1. Point of View: Introducing an Object and Exploring Its Hidden Function

Point of view denotes the distinct perspective and angle from which the object in a film is observed. It manifests throughout the narrative, often remaining unarticulated. By reading with a keen awareness of this concept, one can recognize the pervasive influence of point of view in various story elements. [2] There are usually two points of view to consider when editing a

film: the narrative and the physical. [3] Reading the movie from its narrative point of view, examining it from an inward viewpoint, and comprehending its performance and function are all considered forms of "visionary observation."

Narrative points of view come in a variety. According to Todorov's classification, narrative point of view can be broadly divided into three types: omniscient point of view (narrator > character), internal point of view (narrator = character), and external point of view (narrator < character) [4]. The omniscient narrator always knows more than the characters: the secret desires of the characters, the thoughts of several characters, and the events that the characters do not understand. This point of view might be thought of as a method of "from behind" observation. From the internal point of view, the narrator is just as knowledgeable as the characters; therefore, if the characters are unable to explain the occurrences, the narrator is unable to provide the reader with an explanation. A method of observing "together" (narrator and character), sometimes in the first person and other times in the third, is called an internal point of view. The narrator's reaction to an omniscient point of view that is less knowledgeable than any of the characters in the work is known as the external point of view. This method of witnessing "from the outside" (the narrator) allows him to just describe the characters' speech and actions to the reader while remaining unaware of their innermost thoughts or feelings. [4] Drama and suspense are the traits or benefits of the external point of view, which are useful for engrossing the reader in the reconstruction but unsuitable for accurately capturing the characters. In contrast to the omniscient point of view, both the outward and internal points of view are "points of limited knowledge."

Inner Mongolian films have distinct natural ecosystems, folk rituals, and historical and cultural inheritance, all of which combine to offer a novel experience for viewers. The way the film is seen has a direct impact on the communication outcome, allowing the audience

to see, feel, and experience the distinct culture of that ethnicity or place. In contrast to literature, film is a method of presenting information that primarily impacts the viewer's visual, auditory, and other sensory organs, rather than the cognitive perspective. This frame of view allows for direct and thorough information gathering while remaining subject to sensory limits. For example, if you are at home, you can not look outside without opening the doors and windows. In this scenario, employing an omniscient viewpoint in the narrative might result in a more accurate and realistic image of national and regional cultures. Since the turn of the century, the omniscient point of view has been the most commonly employed narrative premise in inner Mongolian cinema.

Inner Mongolian regional culture consists primarily of natural scenery, historical and cultural landmarks, and folk practices. Being omniscient, the film may express various cultural forms in a comprehensive and relevant way, resulting in improved communication outcomes. In the film "Urtiin Duu," for instance, the inner Mongolian countryside was frequently portrayed as a panorama, sometimes as a long shot with a blank frame and other times as a background, creating an uncomfortable visual impression. had a profound effect on the crowd. Additionally, the audience is shown inner Mongolian cuisine customs, wedding and burial rites, and festivals from the perspective of cognition. The same omniscient but limited point of view is used in "Grey of Time," which shows the same desert scenery, shamans begging for rain, horse-herding ceremonies, fire rituals, and other regional cultural patterns one after the other. For instance, in "Heavenly Grassland," a Chinese child named Huzi portrays the "other." The nature, festivals, fire sacrifices, customs, and straightforward and giving humanity to the herdsmen of the inner Mongolian grasslands are all depicted in great detail by Huzi, who plays the first-person character in this movie from his limited point of view. Huzi needed medical attention because he was mentally "ill" when he got to the steppes of Mongolia. The beautiful grasslands, the straightforward and devoted folk traditions of the inner Mongolian people, and the generosity of herdsmen all helped to heal him. When he eventually won the horse race, he was unable to speak and yelled "Tenger" in inner Mongolian. In this sense, the movie presents regional culture from the narrow viewpoint of the "other," which is not merely a performance and is better able to examine the hidden function of national regional culture than a straightforward omniscient point of view. It is an omniscient effect. As a result, the point of view that is shown in the movie has to do with both the study of the object's function and its real portrayal.

1. The cultural expression of national regions and events

Themes and events that convey regional and national culture are also necessary for inner Mongolian national cinema. "All the events that are given to us or that we can deduce" is what history is. "An arrangement or construction of multiple events in some form or structure" is what is meant by an event.[5] Film is a narrative art form, and its main purpose is to tell a tale from beginning to end. According to Forster's definition, a

plot is similarly an account of events, and a story is generally a chronological record of occurrences. For instance, the narrative "The king died, and shortly the queen also passed away" is an example. Furthermore, the plot of "The king died, and soon the queen too died of grief" [5] In contrast to narrative works like novels, cinema screenplays are more focused on event organization and have a more condensed period. Strive to complete the story within the time frame given, expressing the author's goal completely at the end.

For certain inner Mongolian films, the primary and fundamental goal is to promote and depict the ethnic nation's vibrant culture. But these kinds of performances and ads cannot be as simple as documentaries. Therefore, as the plot develops naturally, the majority of creators expose national and regional cultures. The audience will be able to apply the author's subjective ideas, comprehend the knowledge associated with the story, and identify the effect of the regional culture of a few ethnic groups while they enjoy it. Since the creative planning of events is primarily responsible for achieving this intentional ethos of the inner Mongolian national cinema, it is worthwhile to investigate how the events might be organized to better convey them. There are two broad categories into which inner Mongolian national films from the new century can be categorized in terms of plot and performance impact. One is that narrative hints are quite obvious, the film's plot goes forward, and the depiction of regional culture lacks cohesion and subjectivity. The other type is characterized by imprecise plot hints and a sluggish plot, but the presentation of regional culture is dominant and has excellent continuity.

In the first scenario, a film with a relatively clear storyline shows the audience a clear story with clear characters, ups and downs, plot, development, climax, and ending that are relatively complete. For example, in the film "Urtiin Duu" (inner Mongolian Long Song), Chitsige and her husband Bat visited Beijing to promote inner Mongolian melodies. He was a veterinarian in the Bat Plains, so he moved to Beijing and worked at an equestrian club. In the second situation, for example, a film with ambiguous narrative hints and an unfinished story chain lacks a coherent plot capable of holding the audience's interest. Then, other aspects of the depiction, such as the expression of national and regional culture, might capture the audience's attention and highlight its features. Shilinfu, for instance, is frequently depicted in "Mother" from a diverse perspective and consistently feels cut off from the local cattlemen. Only during the horse-feeding scene does she engage with the local herdsmen. From a narrative perspective, the plot is incomplete, lacks a distinct plot chain, and resembles a "thrust culture" story, which is insufficient to evoke interest in audiences. The character is comparable to a visitor who has arrived in a distant country in this regard. Through his findings and observations, he assesses Mongolia's natural beauty, human emotions, humanity, and traditional practices. Their fate only has significance if it is tied to their national culture. They function as a way to depict regional and national cultures in movies. While the novel is complete, its organization is no longer apparent, compact, cohesive, and

dominant since the events that comprise it are not bound to a certain period.

2. Structure: linear structure, text structure, and national and regional cultural expression

The structure is a key component of Inner Mongolian national films that reflect the culture of the region. In general, structure refers to the location, arrangement, and organization of the different parts of objects; its qualities and integrity serve as the group's means of connection. The film's structure is partly isomorphic to that of real life, making it challenging to categorize into a single, set pattern because it is as intricate and varied as life itself. But in the end, living structures and high-resolution creative structures are not the same. Only a few number of structural shapes are prevalent among the many different kinds. The chronological type, memory type, and time-space intermediate type are examples of basic types from the perspective of time and space. It makes sense to say that there are plays, variations, books, and other genres. Furthermore, even though one structural form dominates the movie, it is impossible to ignore how other structural forms contribute to the script's weaving and create a hybrid structure.

Traditional linear causal, novel, and plot structures are the most often employed structural techniques in movies. A dramatic structure is another name for a linear causal structure that is based on a dramatic conflict and adheres to the rule of cause and effect. The process of conflict development is one of the narrative hints that may be found in structural aspects including beginning, development, the culmination, and ending. [6] However, dramatic structure is not restricted by causality and can take many other shapes. The terms "dramatic" and "causal" cannot be used interchangeably, particularly considering the distinctions between stage plays and movies. Consequently, some scholars think that a "linear causal structure" is a clear definition of the movie's dramatic structure. [7] The novel-style structure is more adaptable to shifts in time and space, with a concentration on gradual structural development rather than chasing great drama. Essay structure is also known as documentary structure or topic change structure, and its defining element is documentary. A single theme rules the entire tale and events, as opposed to variations on a musical theme; it avoids dramatic conflict and does not employ artistic techniques such as metaphors, connections, or flashbacks.

The inner Mongolian film's structure has presented a complex form since the beginning of the century. More linear causal and plot structures are typically employed. Regional cultural presentation will be impacted differently by various structural forms. A common movie with a linear cause-and-effect framework is "Gray of Time." The film tells the narrative of the Urigen family's horse purchase, highlighting the contrast between living on the prairie and life in the city. Finally, to send their son to school, the Urigene family sold their remaining sheep, destroyed their homesteads, and moved to the city. This is a very common linear causal pattern. On the one hand, this form emphasizes the clash between contemporary civilization and livestock farming culture. On the other hand, the rich customs of the national culture and regional characteristics

are perfectly displayed. Also, many inner Mongolian films with script structure may be related to the director's "first" presentation goal. The structural feature of the novel is that the theme is clear but the narrative is not strong, which means that the causal relationship between the plots is unclear or nonexistent. As a structuring force to drive the development of the novel, the plot is inadequate, lacking compactness and coherent dramatic tension, and the prose and poetry. For example, in *The Sky*, the narrative is still told chronologically but seems linear. However, the play as a whole lacks clues to a specific event that could create a dramatic conflict, and the causal connection between events and scenes is very weak. The entire play describes the rural life of Huzi, the son of Han. Therefore, the film does not have a clear and strong dramatic conflict, as is characteristic of the novel. Still, various plots, scenes, and paragraphs are united under a theme and serve as an explanation of the theme. However, because the story is no longer the primary focus in this form, some aspects of the inner Mongolian culture—such as festivals, marriages, and fire rituals—will be emphasized, and the characters' actions will be largely substituted. Structure and size turn into additional forces.

As shown by the two structuring approaches analyzed in this article, national and regional cultural representations appear as structures that emerge in films that adopt a linear causal structure. It is not a structural force that drives the development of the story, but an important factor in the structure and an object of expression implicit in the structure. In a film with a plot structure, the causal connections between the plots are weak and broken, the drama is not strong, and the overall plot is prose and poetry. The area culture is a significant structural element that gives the film a particular "documentary" feel, although the novel is not always an effective structuring force in films. It is challenging to determine which structural approach is more suitable and expressive for inner Mongolian films. It mostly depends on elements like the film's artistic purpose and the reasons behind its release.

3. Conclusion

Inner Mongolian films have always been deeply impacted by the traits and distinguishing features of the national culture. Since the start of the century, as globalization and modernization have increased, cultural conflict and identity anxiety have grown more intense. This video depicts the current state of national culture in the context of globalization and modernity, as well as the uneasy connection with modernism that is central to inner Mongolian films in the new century. This article provides an analysis of the use of perspective, plot, and structure in inner Mongolian national films, emphasizing their relevance to the narrative art of ethnic regional culture. It posits that these elements play a crucial role in the effective dissemination of both national and regional culture. This technical analysis is pertinent to understanding the overall communication impact of films and therefore warrants the attention of both creators and scholars in the field.

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